

Volatile compounds in the vehicle-interior: Odorants of an aqueous cavity preservation and beyond

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Abstract

The smell of the vehicle-interior of cars, especially new cars, can be very distinct. Amongst other sources, we here discuss one material aspect that has hitherto not been further considered: the odour of an aqueous cavity preservation may be perceived in the vehicle interior as volatile compounds of the anti-corrosion agent can easily penetrate the vehicle cabin. To investigate the respective odour-active compounds, an automotive wax-based aqueous cavity preservation was analysed by extracting the volatiles with dichloromethane, followed by isolation of volatiles via solvent-assisted flavour evaporation. Screening via gas chromatography-olfactometry revealed eleven odour-active compounds, of which γ -lactones and carboxylic acids exhibited high odour potency. The results are discussed in relation to other studies focusing on the odorants of materials in the vehicle-interior, where mainly plastics and seat covers have been investigated so far. It is interesting to note that γ -lactones like γ -nonalactone and carboxylic acids like butanoic acid have also been reported in these studies, suggesting that, due to their diverse material sources, these substance classes generally contribute to the odour of the vehicle-interior.

Keywords: cavity wax, vehicle-interior, odour, gas chromatography, olfactometry

Introduction

An aqueous cavity preservation is used in vehicles as a rust prevention agent. It is applied as a liquid to the inner part of the vehicle body and hardens by evaporation of water. Environmental influences such as rain, coastal climate with high salt content or intrusion of road salt into the cavities of a vehicle body favour corrosion in uncoated areas [1]. A cavity preservation consists of waxes which protect the structural parts of the car as a barrier through their hydrophobicity, and thus prevent metal corrosion. Cavity preservations exhibit a typical odour. Negative pressure in a vehicle-interior, caused by an open sunroof or window [2], can thus result in the transfer of this typical odour into the vehicle-interior.

Instrumental analyses of vehicle manufacturers and suppliers mainly target the identification of substances by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and human sensory evaluation is often only performed by rating the overall odour of the car. Thereby, general emissions of single volatile organic compounds into the vehicle-interior have been intensively studied, with the aim of elucidating their impact on the air quality of the indoor air of the passenger cabin [3]. However, sound knowledge with respect to the odour-contributing substances, especially those that are present at trace level, is not yet at hand, especially with respect to aqueous cavity preservations.

To fill this gap, we designed an experimental set-up to first simulate the hardening of an aqueous cavity preservation, and then characterize the odour-active compounds by using GC-O (gas chromatography-olfactometry) and 2D-GC-MS/O (two-dimensional gas chromatography mass-spectrometry/ olfactometry). We then relate the obtained results to previous reports of odorous substances in the car interior and we further discuss potential sources of odorants in the vehicle-interior. Additionally, we provide an overview of the most potent odorants of the materials in the vehicle-interior which have been investigated by GC-O so far.

Experimental

Material

The wax-based aqueous cavity preservation was provided by a paint shop in a vehicle assembly plant of the BMW Group and was obtained as a bulk liquid. Nine g of the liquid aqueous cavity preservation were applied on a 0.05 m² metal sheet ensuring equal distribution and afterwards, the metal sheet was stored in a darkened room with air exchange at ambient temperature to simulate hardening. After seven days, the sample was further investigated.

Sample workup

Solvent extraction was accomplished by stirring 0.68 g of the hardened aqueous cavity preservation in 200 mL dichloromethane (DCM) for 1 h. Subsequently, non-volatile compounds were removed from the volatiles by means of the solvent-assisted flavour evaporation (SAFE) technique [4]. The DCM distillate containing the volatile fraction was then dried, filtered, and concentrated to a total volume of 100 μ L at 50°C by using Vigreux and microdistillation according to Bemelmans [5]. The main odorants detected were identified as described in the following section.

Identification with gas chromatography-olfactometry (GC-O) and two-dimensional gas chromatography with mass spectrometry and olfactometry (2D-GC-MS/O)

The identification of the odour-active compounds was based on the comparison of odour quality, retention indices on two capillaries with different polarities and mass spectra with those of authentic reference compounds. GC-O was performed using a gas chromatograph (TRACE GC Ultra; Thermo Fischer Scientific, Waltham, USA) equipped with a cold on column injector on a DB-5 or DB-FFAP capillary column, respectively (both 30 m x 0.32 mm, film thickness 0.25 μ m; J & W Scientific Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA). At the end of the capillary, the effluent was split into two equal parts and transferred to a sniffing port and a flame ionization detector (FID). Retention indices were calculated for each odour-active compound by means of a reference series of homologous alkanes (C₆-C₃₀) [6].

Mass spectra were obtained with a 2D-GC-MS/O system (two Agilent 7890B GC and Agilent 5977B MS; Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, US). The first GC was equipped with a cold on column injector and a DB-FFAP capillary column, the second GC was coupled to the first oven with a cryo-trap system and contained a DB-5 capillary column (column details see GC-O). After one part of the effluent was transferred onto the second oven and was injected by thermodesorption, the effluent of the first GC was split again into a sniffing port and an FID. The effluent of the second GC was split by transferring the compounds to a mass spectrometer as well as to a sniffing-port. Mass spectra were generated at 70 eV ionization energy in the electron impact mode with a m/z range from 35 to 400.

Results and discussion

Identification of odorants of the aqueous cavity preservation

Analysis via GC-O revealed a series of odour-active compounds that clearly belonged to a set of substance groups that were primarily dominated by lactones and acids. Representative substances of both groups are displayed in figure 1. Eleven of these substances were successfully identified according to the above-mentioned identification criteria. Primarily the coconut-like, fruity and peach-like smelling homologous series of γ -lactones from γ -octalactone to γ -undecalactone and the cheesy, musty, coriander-like and soapy smelling carboxylic acids butanoic acid, octanoic acid, decanoic acid and undecanoic acid and vanillin are, to the best of our knowledge, reported here for the first time as odorous constituents of an aqueous cavity preservation for usage in cars.

The identified substances have already been reported as odorants in non-food materials, especially in waxes [7]. The formation of lactones could be explained by reactions initiated by environmental factors, e.g. heat, light, or radiation [8, 9], and the same formation process can, accordingly, be suspected for the formation of the identified δ -nonalactone. In addition, generation of the carboxylic acids is also supported by heat, light, or radiation, and potential formation pathways have already been suggested [7]. Consequently, odorous acids are also likely to be found in different olefins and waxes. Vanillin is also a well-known odorant and has already been reported in diverse non-food materials [7, 10].

Figure 1: Identified odorants and their odour qualities in the hardened aqueous cavity preservation.

Odorants of the cavity preservation in the context of previously reported odorants of the vehicle-interior

To date, the odorants of only a few materials of the vehicle-interior have been investigated by olfactometric techniques, namely plastic and leather materials. In Table 1 we provide an overview of the predominantly investigated materials together with their prominent odorants. All in all, mainly plastics and seat covers have been investigated so far by means of GC-O, based on the consideration that these materials exhibit a large surface area and could, as a result, strongly contribute to the interior odour of a car. In addition to the visible construction materials of the vehicle-interior, however, other aids such as lubricants and adhesives are used in vehicle construction and could also contribute to the overall smell in the passenger cabin [11]. In this respect, we were the first to investigate one of these materials.

When comparing the most potent odorants of the investigated materials of the vehicle-interior, it becomes evident that 1-hexen-3-one has been repeatedly observed as one of the main odorants in three different plastic materials. Despite the noticeable prevalence of this plastic-like smelling and pungent compound, the formation of 1-hexen-3-one is still unknown [10]. The fatty, cardboard-like smelling aldehydes (*E*)-2-nonenal and (*Z*)-2-nonenal, on the other hand, are likely to be formed via oxidation of unsaturated fatty acids [12]. Besides their occurrence in foods, these compounds have also been detected in various non-food materials. Trace remnants of fats in thermoplastic polyolefin and leather could lead to the formation of these potent odorants [11]. The third group of potent odorants in the materials were the substituted phenols, like the phenolic smelling 2-*tert*-butylphenol and smoky smelling 2-methoxyphenol. Degradation of phenolic antioxidants like butylated hydroxy toluene can be proposed as precursors forming such odorants in materials of the vehicle-interior [11].

Table 1: Overview of materials of the vehicle-interior investigated by GC-O.

Material	Most potent odorants	Reference
Polyvinylchloride based artificial leather	1-hexen-3-one, acetophenone, 1-octen-3-one	[13]
Polypropylene materials	1-hexen-3-one, butanoic acid, 4-methylphenol, 1-butanol, 2- <i>tert</i> -butylphenol	[10]
Thermoplastic polyolefin	2,3-butanedione, 1-hexen-3-one, methional, (<i>Z</i>)-2-nonenal, (<i>E</i>)-2-nonenal, 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline	[11]
Polyurethane foam	2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine	[11]
Polyphenyloxide material	2-methoxyphenol, methyl phenols, dimethyl, phenols	[11]
Leather	γ -nonalactone, vanillin, (<i>E</i>)-2-nonenal, 4-ethyl-2-methoxyphenol, 4-chloro-3-methylphenol	[14, 15]

When comparing the odorants of the aqueous cavity preservation with the common odorants of the investigated materials of the vehicle-interior it becomes evident that carboxylic acids and lactones have already previously been reported. Butanoic acid was identified in polypropylene materials [10] whereas γ -nonalactone and vanillin were detected in leather [14, 15], leading to the suggestion that these substance classes generally contribute to the smell of the passenger cabins.

The aqueous cavity preservation is of especially high interest here as it comes directly into contact with air that can pass to a relevant extent into the vehicle-interior. Future studies of our group will therefore target the question, which compounds exert the main impact on car smell, and which sources are the most prominent with respect to smell. This will be the basis for optimizing materials for technical applications, or to develop the respective substitutes.

Conclusion

For the first time, an anti-corrosion agent for an automotive application was investigated regarding its odour. As odorants, γ -lactones and carboxylic acids were identified as characteristic odorous constituents of the aqueous cavity preservation. The successful identification of potent odorants in this agent encourages further investigations on materials that are used in the vehicle interior, and to optimize their composition regarding a future avoidance of odour generation. In other fields, such approaches are already successfully implemented into the design and development of odour-optimized products, examples are plastic and leather [15, 16]. Nevertheless, to achieve a comprehensive smell optimization, all materials used in car production need to be taken into consideration.

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